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Revised Word Questionnaire (Oct 2003)

Depending on the structure of the language, you may need to consult the questions in a reversed order (e.g. look at stress patterns before looking at phonological rules of assimilation, etc)

For assistance with terms you can consult Bickel's Programm und Verzeichnis der verfügbaren Materialien (on the server)

Or, refer to the .pdf version of the Bickel & Nichols chapter on inflectional morphology (<http://www.uni-leipzig.de/%7ebickel/research/papers/index.html>)

PHONETIC & PHONOLOGICAL QUESTIONS

You should note forms that the author overtly *describes* (and also covertly *treats*) as phonologically independent. I am especially interested in the *crucial* differences between what is possible (or highly common) within a phonologically independent unit and what is possible at the *edges* or across boundaries

As you investigate, make an inventory-style comparison of patterns/processes that apply to independent forms with both lexical content and grammatical content. Note what is possible within the form's internal boundaries versus what is possible at the edges (especially if the form is polysyllabic). For example, note possible and required consonant onsets at the initial edge of an independent unit, and compare these to the same onset patterns within the unit.

If an author says something like "no final consonants" or "no consonants in final position", always check to see if this constraint holds up at syllable edges *within* a phonologically independent form, and at the *ending* edge of the form itself.

Note also that a form may be phonologically "free" or independent, while not necessarily constituting a lexical category (i.e. "noun" or "verb" or "adjective"). I am especially interested in grammatical forms that are phonologically independent (and also lexical forms that are phonologically dependent upon something else—cannot occur alone phonologically, but they express a meaning that you might otherwise think of as "word")

Always take from the grammar at least 1 useful example of each thing.

Look for contradictory or conflicting phenomena (e.g. stress pattern A applies in almost all cases except...). This may be important. In some larger phonological units, one criterion may apply, but the other may suggest a different organization of units.

1. Segmental & Phonotactic Patterns (edges vs. internal)

- occurrence of segments, limitations, prohibitions
- voicing, aspiration patterns
- manner patterns (plosive, affricate, fricative, tap, approx, etc.)
- place (either specific like bilabial, lamino-dental, or general like anterior, coronal, etc.)
- gemination
- vowel height/backness (quality)
- nasal vowels (see "rules")
- vowel length
- VV sequences (includes diphthongs)
- idiosyncratic, segment-specific restrictions or possibilities, like "no labiodental approximants at starting edge, even though they occur medially etc."

The following restrictions apply for any root or any other form that may stand as an independent word-unit (see below for the different morphological categories of things that are and are not words)

- The C inventory has only voiced stops, but these are occasionally partially devoiced when pw(
 - a "tendency" for ɲ, ŋ, n to be deleted when)pw, and if this happens then the word-final vowel becomes lengthened and nasalized: V>Ṽ: /_)pw (after C deletion)
 - within a word, d >ɸ when intervocalic: /bindada/ = [bindaɸa]
 - l > ɭ / u_)pw (so has to both follow u and be at back edge of word)
 - a Vn or Vŋ sequence > Ṽ /)pw: galiŋ)w > [galĩ], but not galiŋala > *[galiãla]
 - g > g^w / pw(__u-ŋ)g or pw(__u-u (not sure if the main trigger is wd edge or vowel conditioning)
 - *l / w(__ (except for English loans)
 - there is no word that is i(:)yC)w
 - ŋ and w not permitted word-finally underlyingly, but may occur as final segment in monosyllabic inflectional suffixes, and I guess if it occurs wd-final, it is the result of a process like final syllable deletion (see below)
 - u is never word-final, and never occurs in 3-syllable roots. It is the least frequently occurring vowel of the 3 vowels, and it displays a general dispreference for being in bigger words or being word-final
 - Dixon notes that vowel length differences are "more dramatic" at word-final edge than at initial edge (but wouldn't this be expected anyway because there are no long V's as VI?)
 - A pword cannot end with a C cluster, but this is possible: V:C)pword (after v. length & final deletion rules have applied--see below)
- e.g. ginda:n 'moon'
ɟambu:l 'two'
waŋa:ɭ 'youth'
mala:n 'right hand'

2. "Rules" Part 1

Some phonological processes are restricted in application to the internal domain of a phonologically independent unit, and others are restricted to the boundaries/edges. Sometimes these differences are explicitly noted, others may be implicit. Please list the major processes that highlight such boundaries. Do these things happen to lexical forms only, to grammatical forms only, or to both?

Note types and locations of:

--vowel/consonant HARMONY/assimilation/dissimilation (note the types—place, manner, voicing, other)

--segment DELETION/epenthesis, any kind of insertion/deletion processes

--segment METATHESIS or any type of re-ordering

A couple of rules that seem to appeal directly to word boundaries:

1. V-lengthening rule

in each word that has an odd number of syllables (underlyingly), the penult vowel should be lengthened (V>V:)

e.g. /muʃam/ > [muʃam] 'mother' (because even # syllables)

but,

/muʃam + -gu/ > [muʃa:m-gu] 'mother.DAT' --shows that the suffix is part of the word (underlyingly), and its addition creates a condition for v lengthening

note the difference here though:

/gudaga/ > [guda:ga] 'dog' (odd # σ underlyingly)

BUT

/gudaga + -gu/ > [gudaga-gu] 'dog.DAT' (even # σ underlyingly)

2. Final syllable deletion rule

XVIC1(C2)V2w > XVIC1w (so, a deletion (C)V sequence at wd edge)

IF:

a. the pre-deleted root has odd # σ

AND

b. the coda C of the preceding σ has these segments: l, r, ʃ, y, m, ɲ, ɳ

AND

c1. XVC1 of preceding σ

or

c2. V2= A, I, U (special vowels)

AND

only a σ that is open can be deleted, so if the target x is VC, then I guess it is exempted.

Ultimately, minimally a V may be deleted, but a CV may also be targeted for deletion

This rule interacts with the V length rule, it is ordered after the length rule.

e.g. /buʃa + ɳgu/ 'woman + erg'

1. *v. length* > buŋa:ŋgu

2. *delete odd (C)V at)w* > [buŋa:ŋ]

Underlyingly, the long vowel and final velar nasal would not be permitted. We can see that they are the result of a process of rules, that the rules are ordered, and that the rules are sensitive to word structure/boundaries.

We can see that this rule is not applicable when there are disyllabic affixes present, because by virtue of their own word status, they do not participate in triggering the rule. However, the monosyllabic affixes participate in this rule--their presence may promote the conditions for this rule to kick in (see below for more complete listing of which infl/deriv. affixes are words, and those which are not).

Note: Dixon says that there is a very small set of nominal roots that do have inherent vowel length in word-final position. Their V: patterns cannot be accounted for by any processes and defy the overall word-structure patterns. e.g. /yabu:/ 'species of grass' and /uuɽu:/ 'river'

Other rules--appear to apply only within a pword, and never at edges:

1. *segmental assimilation, such as what happens at morpheme-boundary between ergative and locative suffixes. These suffixes are monosyllabic, and contribute to a pword (are not their own pwords)*

2. *nasal insertion--Dixon says this is a marginal process and happens across morpheme boundaries within the pword, not at edges.*

3. "Rules" Part 2

Some rules referring to possible (and prohibited) syllable structures, processes of syllabification, and also to suprasegmental processes are sensitive to the domain of a phonologically independent unit. The distribution of these processes may help to define the boundaries and internal composition of such units.

Note:

--THE DEFAULT syllable template, and whether or not this template applies to the edges of phonologically free units. For example, a language may allow C clusters in coda position, but this may only happen at the ending edge of a phon. free unit, and not internally (or the other way around)

The default template for roots is minimally disyllabic: CIVIC2V2(C2V2)(C3) syllable begins with a single C and contains a single V segment. It may end with a single V or a single C.

Any phonetic monosyllable has a "very long" vowel [V::], and are analyzed phonologically as disyllabic (longer than a CV:)

so [bu::m] is realized as /buwum/ 'vine'

with this minimal size, the default syllable template = the word

The Yidiny consonants: b, d, g, m, n, w, y, r, l, ɽ, ɲ (pal nas) , ɟ (vd. pal plos), ŋ,

The vowels: a, i, u

r=triled apic. rhotic

y=semi-vow laminal

l=apical lateral

*V1 can be any short V, implies that *[V:] / w(*

V2 can be any short or long V

C1 can be any stop, nasal, w or y

C3 = l, r, ʃ, y, m, n, ɲ

but C3 cannot be ŋ (so words cannot end with ŋ)

C2 can be any C or a number of cluster types: any homorganic nasal-obs cluster (e.g.

mb, nd, ɲɲ, ŋg), can be a cluster of l, r or ʃ followed by b, ɟ, g, m, ɲ, ŋ, mb, ɲɲ, ŋg, w,

can also be nb, nɲ, ng, can also be a cluster of l plus nb, nɲ, ng

can also be a w-cluster or y-cluster where second segment can be b, g, m, ŋ, mb, ŋg, or

finally, a yw cluster.

so it also looks like clusters cannot occur either word-initially or word finally, only in medial position. See comments about syllabification issues for clusters.

Dixon notes that the disyllabic affixes (both infl and derivational) conform to same patterns. The monosyllabic suffixes (they are not words) have some "eccentricities"--suggesting even more so that they are not pwords.

see section 1 for constraints on where individual segments may/may not occur

--C COMBOS—are the same types permitted both internally and at edges?

--syllabification patterns (across syllables internally, vs. across morphemes, vs. across independent units)

--SUPER heavy syllables (Hall 2001). Can something that is phonologically free end with a super-heavy syllable? Or can such syllables only be in an internal position? What are the types (e.g. CV:C; CVVC: CVCC)? Can all types occur *anywhere* in a phon. free unit? Note even any seemingly idiosyncratic restrictions (like, might a certain suffix never co-occur with a SHS?, etc.)

1 type of super-heavy syllable is optionally possible only within a word boundary. This has to do with optional syllable parsing when there is a C-cluster medially.

General syllable boundaries: V.CV and VC.CV

But if there is a series of more than 2 C's within a word, both options are possible:

VCC.CV and VC.CCV

So, the first of these options is super-heavy

here are some words that can be parsed to (optionally) have a SHS word-medially:

bayŋga 'hot cooking stone'

barŋga 'praise'

dulnbilay 'white cedar'

burmbuʃ 'palm tree'

burɲi 'finish off (vb)'

burŋga 'snore (vb)'

ɲarmbi 'approach the ground, but not reach it (vb)'

murŋgal 'short feather'

darŋgidarŋgi 'old woman' (always reduplicated)

even loans can be optionally parsed like this: *bilayŋgir* 'blanket, loan from eng.'

--STRESS It might be a good idea to look at stress rules first, as these can often clearly illuminate boundaries of phonologically free units—especially if the language only allows "1 main stress per word" or something of that nature. You can then work "backwards" and look at other cues to independent status.

--is there a primary stress rule? what is the domain?

--what types of forms are included, what is exempted?

--what are the minimal/maximal domains for stress to apply? Can a phonologically free unit that is simply (C)V take the main stress?

--can only lexical forms take a main stress, or can independent grammatical forms also take it?

Stress rule in Yidiny:

Stress the first syllable with V:

if there is no V:, then stress the initial syllable

In each pword there is stress alternation

A long vowel always primarily attracts the primary stress

So a word with two long vowels will have an odd number of syllables, with every other syllable being stressed--this satisfies both the V: stress and the alternating stress requirements.

Dixon notes that most words have an even number of syllables (so that must mean that most words have no more than 1 V:)

--TONE Again, another good starting place if other cues are hard to find. Is the domain of tone a syllable? morpheme? phonologically free unit? If the language has syllabic tone, there may still be a word-level domain at work, like "only 1 high per phon. free unit" or something else like this. If grammatical forms take tone, do they also have other features that might suggest that they can stand alone phonologically (like the other stuff listed above)? N/A

--"PITCH ACCENT" In some languages, the apparent tonal contrasts are not clearly defined until they occur on a "larger" unit. Describe the morphological and/or syllabic complexities of such units N/A

4. Minimality & Maximality

Look at the grammar, look also at the dictionary/glossary entries if they are included. What is the most common (or only) minimal and maximal size of a phon. free unit? Or alternatively, what is the minimal/maximal morphological complexity/composition of something that is phonologically free? (C)V? CV (with an initial crucially present)? di- or polysyllable? How big can a free unit be in terms of syllable number? Do these size

constraints apply only to lexical forms? If there are constraints, must a lexical form be bimorphemic to be free? If so, what morphemes qualify? Any & all?

*Dixon says: no pword is "abnormally long" (no more than 7 syllables)
He says he's seen a root + up to 4 cohering suffixes*

5. Reduplication

Is the entire unit copied? More? Less? Can something of any phonological size/ complexity have reduplication (even if the process is semantically restricted)? If there are different *types* of reduplication, see if you can find patterns, or note what the author says.

Is the resulting suprasegmental pattern of a reduplicated form the same or different from a single free form? (Are there 2 main stresses or 1? 2 tones? a different tone altogether?)

Reduplication in Yidiny:

looks like only nominals have redup. with a general "plural" meaning

The pattern: copy the first 2 syllables of a root

e.g. bu.ɲa 'woman' > buɲa.buɲa 'women'

mu.la.ri 'initiated man' > mula.mulari 'initiated men'

The coda of the 2nd syllable does not copy if it is homorganic with a following stop C

If there is a deletion rule involved (see above), then the reduplication uses the pre-deleted form

e.g. /ɟabiɽ + -da/ 'flat rocks.LOTS'

penult length rule > ɟabi:ɽda

deletion rule > [ɟabi:ɽ] 'lots of flat rocks'

but reduplicated form is this:

[ɟabiɟ.ɟabi:da] 'on lots of flat rocks'

the pre-rule form was copied

This shows that a pword was copied, but also the above example shows that the resulting reduplicated form is 2 pwords (not 1). We know this by the position of primary stress.

The stress rule says "stress the first V: in the wd, and if no V:, stress the initial" So the only V: gets stress in the reduplicated form.

and it seems to defy the above processes, because it pays attention to the pre-rule-affected root

6. Other Questions

Note any discussion & descriptions of phonological boundaries attributed to interruption or pause phenomena. Also note if the author argues for boundaries because of repair phenomena. Examples. Only in the more detailed grammars will you probably see such discussions.

7. Phonological Units in Morphologically Complex Forms

--COMPOUNDING: note any patterns of segmental alteration with compounds—especially at the edges of compounds; note prior and resulting stress/tone patterns; note segmental restrictions in compounds (e.g. in Manange, the 2nd element may never have an aspirated onset, even if the onset of the form when it is free is aspirated). Again, note any conflicts of properties (e.g. in Lhasa Tibetan, a compound has 2 tone contours, but there is vowel harmony that spreads across the entire compound, and only a single main stress)
Sometimes in a compound, a piece of one of the elements may be deleted. If this happens, note any patterns, because this may suggest that one of the elements is in fact not a single phonological unit.

Compounding in Yidiny

A fairly restricted process in general. Verbs be compounds in a kind of "noun-incorporation" form (noun + verb = verb) and a couple of nominal compounding possibilities

1. verbal compounds--2 roots (noun + verb) combine to form a verb. There is no phonological incorporation of the noun into the verb--the noun remains a separate pword, and has a disyllabic minimal size:

e.g. (ɟili) 'eye' + (budi) 'put.down' > (ɟili)(budi) 'to look after'

But there is some evidence that the resulting form is 1 gword:

--there are ordering restrictions (unless meaning is changed)

--the syntactic function is a unified one

--there is a general semantic output that does not necessarily correspond to the individual meanings of the 2 elements involved

another example:

(guybil) 'whistle.noise' + (ɟana) 'stand.INTR' > (guybil)(ɟana) 'to whistle'

stress not marked in these examples, but my guess is that each initial syllable gets main stress.

2. Proper Noun Compounds--same processes, same results

--"SIMPLE juxtaposition or concatenation of 2+ independent forms" —these are things that might be called "serialization" in some grammars: note any phonological discussion of these things. single tone? single stress? segment changes? ordering restrictions? co-occurrence restrictions?

--MULTI-morphemic forms: this is already discussed in above sections, but note especially phonologically free units that are minimally bimorphemic (or bigger), note any allomorphy that suggests that multi-morphemic forms behave as a single phonological unit.

--IF a language has a wide variety of inflectional affixes, do all stem-affix combinations have the same/similar stress, syllabification, segmental patterns, phon rules, tones, etc? Describe those that deviate from the set "general" patterns. Give examples. In German, for example, a stem + certain suffixes behaves as a **single** phonological unit ([li:.bɪ] 'love 1.sg'), but a stem + certain other suffixes behaves as **2** phonological units ([li:p.liç] 'dearly')—the resyllabification & voicing of the plosive is evidence of this.

Be sensitive to exceptions/variations in segmental/phonotactic, prosodic rules that may suggest that certain things "go together" phonologically, and others that do not. Explicitly state the conditions under which variations apply.

MORPHOLOGY & SYNTAX QUESTIONS

The goal here is to identify individual grammatical forms (or combinations of forms) as independent units (grammatical units/grammatical words). In some cases, these forms (or combinations of) exist as syntactic units, at other times as morphological units. Still other times, the distinctions will be collapsed or blurred. The primary interest here is not whether or not they are phonologically independent, although it is important to note whether or not the things you're describing are free or bound. This is because we will be creating a 3rd dedicated database that charts the overlaps/alignments between things that are phonologically free and things that are morpho-syntactically free.

8. Create a (glossed) list of inflectional morphemes (the types) described. Note the distribution of each morpheme:

--with what **MUST** they co-occur (bound or free)?

--with what else **MAY** they (optionally) co-occur (bound or free)?

--if they co-occur with multiple different types of forms (either as a host or attached to a host), are the resulting meanings always the same, or are they different? Note the differences with examples.

--can other elements ever be inserted between morpheme forms that comprise a stem + infl. form unit? See if adverbs can do this.

Here are some forms that Dixon says are sensitive to above criteria of pword

first, all noun and verb roots are their own pwords

second, any gram form that is its own pword is called "noncohering"

one critical difference between non-cohering affixes & roots: while both may be their own pword, roots may be bigger than 2 syllables, but no non-cohering affix is ever bigger

than disyllabic

a. inflectional elements

classifiers--they are disyllabic and do not contribute to a root's p-rules

e.g. mayi 'edible plant type'; bana 'drinkable liquid type' (etc.)

time adverbials/time words are pwords--disyllabic

b. derivational elements (they all derive a stem belonging to a diff pos)

nominal derivational morphemes (14 types)

verbal derivational morphemes (7 types)

comitative affix /muɔay/

privative affix /gimbal/

'with alot of' affix /damba/

'something, belonging to' /bara/

'only, all' /ɔamu/

'lots, all' /muɔgal/

These gram forms are not their own pwords (they are all monosyllabic):

nominal case affixes

4 types of nominal derivational affixes

locational and temporal affixes

verbal affixal inflections like aspect and tense

5 types of verbal derivational affixes

some verbal infl affixes: past (ɔu), purposive (na and variants)

some time affixes (may ~ m)

case suffix comitative -ɔi ~yi

genitive case -ni

some, I'm not sure of gram status, but they are not pwords:

-da 'fear'

set-inclusive suffix -ba

'another one' -bi

cohering suffixes can stack onto a root, and they appear to simultaneously (as a group)

trigger relevant phon. rules:

/gudaga + yi + ɔu/

penult V length rule: gudagayi:ɔu

delete syllable V rule: [gudagayi:ɔ]

Dixon says there is one clear-cut prefix in the whole lg.: ɔa:-

It appears to be non-cohering (special because it is monosyllabic), it has a limited occurrence in restricted contexts, maybe a form of Jawa, maybe means something like 'mouth/door'

9. Note the overall constituent ordering patterns in the language. Is the pattern rigid, somewhat fluid, very fluid? Do all inflectional/grammatical elements that are called "free" follow the same ordering possibilities as lexical elements? Do they consistently appear in a single ordering scheme or co-occurrence scheme despite being phonologically independent. Pay special attention to so-called particles, or other minimally free forms.

10. Does the author discuss grammatical forms/combinations with a conventionalized meaning or coherence? In other words, are there grammatical combinations with 1 meaning, and that meaning is lost or irretrievable (or totally different) when a piece of the form is missing or when the form is analyzed piece-by-piece? "Constructions" might be a way that grammarians describe this.

11. Are there elements with some degree of ordering or grammatical freedom, but that seem to be phonologically bound? Describe their distribution. Are there elements that appear to be phonologically independent (see above criterion), but have a fixed order or co-occurrence constraint? Describe these too. Pay special attention to things the author calls clitics.

Locational words--they appear to be grammatically versatile, but always their own pword (disyllabic)

When they function as a suffix, they have a restricted application and co-occurrence, but they can also be used in root-like form, where they are both a gword and a pword

e.g.

waŋgi 'up'

jiŋgu 'down'

Then Dixon also describes these particle-like elements:

seem to be their own pword, but also may be a gword, may not be a gword

they are disyllabic, do not condition phon rules in a root/stem

They do not take most/all verbal inflections (unlike verb roots), but they do supply some modal information

e.g.

ŋuʒu 'not, never'-usually immediately precedes a vb or adj. but can take a post-inflectional affix

giyi 'don't'--never takes affixes, nor locational info.

guʒi 'neg imperative' may precede an imperative verb

gana 'try' preferred position is immediately preceding the verb, but it may also occur sentence-initial. It can co-occur with other participial forms.

There are a total of 20 of these types of forms

Lastly, there are things that he calls "post-inflectional affixes". These are not exactly the same as non-cohering affixes, but they are similar.

They are often disyllabic, but some a monosyllabic. They do not trigger or participate in the phon rules that apply to pwords--they appear to affix to the root after the rules.

Dixon proposes a possible explanation--they may be on the verge of becoming their own grammatical words, they may be recently truncated forms, like maybe old roots.

12. Is a grammatical unit always bigger than a single morpheme? Always the same size? Are there some grammatical units that are a single morpheme, but others that are combinations? What is the biggest possible grammatical unit in the language (in terms of numbers of morphemes), and what is the smallest? Pay attention to, for example, the NP, and then also the elements that make up the NP. Then, note the predicate, and then the things that make up the predicate (may be called the "verbal complex").

In Yidiny

It looks like minimally a pword = a gword (a single pword is minimally a disyllabic n or v root)

A gword can be comprised of 2+ pwords (a root + a number of non-cohering affixes)

It does not look like the reverse is true; in other words, I have not found an instance of a single pword being comprised of multiple gwords. I have not, for example, seen particle + affix combos that would = a pword. I have not encountered roots that are not pwords and that must combine with another form of some sort to be a pword. Even the particle-forms and the single prefix are non-cohering or post-lexical, suggesting they possess some form of phonological autonomy, even if their distribution is restricted.

It looks like a pword can be multi-morphemic, but it is actually 1 gword. The resulting form is a root (pword) + multiple cohering affixes. However these affixes are not their own gwords--they have co-occurrence and ordering restrictions. The resulting multimorphemic form is 1 gword and 1 pword.

13. Looking at the main verbal complex in the grammar, how morphologically complex is it? Looking at the predicate of the clause, how many verbs or verb-like elements must be present? verb-only? verb + aux form? 2 + verbs? If aux forms appear, is there a minimal amount (like, there must be at least 1 aux), or is there a maximal amount (like, there can be no more than 3...). In English, for example, in the predicate, there can be just 1 verb (=gword), but there can maximally be up to 1 verb plus 3 or so other gword forms (auxiliaries plus the main verb). (degree of synthesis)